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TEACHER AS TIKTOK

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There is no greater profession that one would not trade
For the noble mission, the youth are invoked
Wisdom is imparted, abilities are showcased
With a heart full of compassion, Goodness is ingrained,

In the face of the pandemic, truly many have suffered
But the resolve for progress, with knowledge as the aspiration, did not waver
Technology skills were nurtured, diligently and painstakingly pursued
So that the hope of the youth lifting us up would not be halted

Like the TIKTOK app, modern activities were embraced
Collaboration was fostered, various stories were presented
Grooving to the music of the new situation gathered
A mix of emotions in singing aspirations and dreams

You are important in the group, your contribution cannot be discarded
You are crucial in the recovery, come, let us rise together
In adversity, let us raise the banner of Education
You are a comrade, TEACHER of the entire community

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